

Developing the Needs of Comprehensive Guidance Sensitization among Teachers of Secondary Schools in West Bengal – An Exploration towards Conscience

Goutam Bandyopadhyay

Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math

ABSTRACT : The world we live in is changing so fast, everyday a bit by bit, that compels us to be in utter alienation, to be in a drift of adjustment and success. Everyday the printing as well as the electronic media highlights the untimely wastage of youth on account of various socio-economic and socio-cultural reasons caused by the the drift mentioned. This blooming passing away used to happen due to lack of proper and timely intervention of guidance. School-going adolescents being allured by charismatic beacon of future, face unique and diverse challenges, competitions and conflicts now-a-days, both personally and developmentally, that immensely influence their academic achievement. This paper has delineated the role of teachers in guiding their students sincerely with the most essential but minimum requisites. No matter whether infrastructure will be available or not, administrative inclination or resentment, environmental support or restraint. Mere sympathy is not enough – a strong goodwill, determination and boundless empathy are extremely urgent in favour of guidance service in schools.

Keywords : Guidance, sensitization, strategies, orientation, development, Academic achievement.

Introduction

World is changing very fast with its fleeting values and transient realization. Today's young people are living in an exciting time, with an interestingly diverse and mobile society, new technologies, and expanding opportunities. To help ensure that they are prepared to become the next generation of parents, workers, leaders

and citizens, every student needs support, guidance and opportunities during adolescence, a time of rapid growth and change. School-going adolescents face unique and diverse challenges, both personally and developmentally that impact academic achievement. Due to rapid changes in society, young people require continuous and comprehensive guidance more than ever before

to enable them make proper education and career choices and to acquire the right skills for a successful adjustment to their environment. The secret of good education consists in enabling the students to realize what are their talents and aptitudes and in what manner and to what extent they can best develop them so as to achieve proper social adjustment and seek right type of employment. Thus guidance means a process of rendering assistance or suggestions to any individual by another for the proper development of personality. It is the process of helping an individual to discover and develop his educational, vocational, psychological potentialities and thereby to achieve an optimum level of personal happiness and social usefulness. The Education Commission (1964-66) considered that the "guidance services have a much wider scope and function than merely that of assisting students in making educational and vocational choices. The aims of guidance are both adjustive and developmental; it helps the student in making the best possible adjustments to the situations in the educational institution and in the home and at the same time facilitates the development of all aspects of his personality. Guidance, therefore, should be regarded as an integral part of education and not special psychological or social service which is peripheral to educational purposes. It is meant for all students, not just for those who deviate from the norm in one direction or the other. It is also a continuous process aimed at assisting the individual to make decisions and adjustments from time to time." Hence, guidance involves the difficult art of helping boys and girls to plan their own future wisely in the full light of all the factors that can be mastered about themselves and about the world in which they are to live and work. Guidance, in this sense, is not confined to the vocational field only. It covers the whole gamut

of youth problems and should be provided in an appropriate form at all stages of education through the co-operative endeavour of understanding parents, teachers, headmasters/headmistress and guidance officer. The basic approach is developmental rather than remedial. Therefore, 'effective education is guidance, and realistic guidance is self-guidance.'

Objectives of the Study

- (1) To serve the students' needs in the present and the future, preparing them to meet their life-goals in a strife-torn environment.
- (2) To give cordial attention to the personal, educational and vocational needs of the individual and for that to maintain good, empathetic relationship between teachers and pupils within a caring ethos.
- (3) To promote the development of students' self-awareness including an understanding of their attitudes and behaviour, abilities, interests and values and also to develop an effective study skills and learning habits.
- (4) To broaden students' horizons by introducing them to the variety of educational opportunities available and the educational routes to each after schooling.
- (5) To understand and facilitate positive change in school environment, in students' decision-making, problem-solving, interpersonal and communication skills.
- (6) To prove leadership in organizing developmental guidance experiences for all students within a school.

- (7) To arrange orientation or sensitization programmes/Workshops among parents and teachers in Ward/Block stages.

Needs are within the Teacher's self: What's more we need

The Guidance Programme, like any other educational programme, requires careful and consistent development. This ensures that the programme responds to the unique needs of its clients. It provides benefits to students by addressing their intellectual, emotional, social and psychological needs. For any guidance programme to meet successfully the needs of all students, it must be developmental, Preventive and remedial rather than crisis-oriented. Further, a comprehensive and developmental guidance and counselling programme is not only preventive but also pro-active in preventive orientation. Consequently, it must be well-planned, goal-oriented and accountable. It is an integral part of the school programme, and complements other important school activities. It should help students who are growing up in a complex world to develop into full human beings, capable of maximizing their potentialities in all personal, educational, social and career-related contexts.

Certain factors which have contributed to the emergent needs for guidance in schools may be mentioned.

- a) Inadequacy of home and community to meet the ever-increasing and complex needs of pupils today.
- b) Greater realization of the inadequacy of classroom instruction to meet the extra-instructional needs of pupils.
- c) The unprecedented increase in the number of school-going children and consequent inability of the teacher to

cope with many problems emerging out of this situation.

d) Drastic Fall in Moral Values

Secondary school or High School is the final transition into adulthood and the world of work as students begin separating from parents and exploring and defining their independence. During these years, students are evaluating their strengths, weaknesses, skills and abilities. They are searching for a place to belong and rely on peer acceptance and feedback. They face increased pressures regarding risk behaviour involving conflicts, tensions etc. while exploring the boundaries of more acceptable behaviour. They need guidance in making concrete and compounded decisions.

Organization of guidance services in schools is needed due to the following advantages which prove its importance.

How are students benefitted for the programme :-

- (i) Understanding of themselves, i.e., their abilities, aptitudes, interest, personality traits, their strengths and weaknesses.
- (ii) Developing their potentialities in the right manner
- (iii) Selection of subjects, books, hobbies, co-curricular activities and preparing from the examination point of view.
- (iv) Selection of occupation, preparing for it, entering in it and to make suitable progress in it.
- (v) Solving personal, emotional and social problems
- (vi) Making education, vocational and psychological adjustments.

How are teachers benefitted for the programme:-

- (i) Understanding their students, i.e., their abilities, aptitudes, interests, personality patterns, their strengths and weaknesses, their emotional and social characteristics, affection, self-recognition, their physical condition, family background and achievements through intelligence test, aptitude test, personality test, interest inventories, and various other data collection techniques such as questionnaire, interview, rating scale, case history, cumulative record, anecdotal record, autobiography and sociometry.
- (ii) Developing their potentialities by detecting maladjustments among students and solving their problems.
- (iii) Improving classroom relationships and emotional climate through emphasis upon democratic procedures.
- (iv) Providing Educational, vocational and psychological guidance
- (v) Preventing crimes and delinquencies which may lead to mental illness.

How are parents sensitized by the programme:-

- (i) Understanding the abilities, aptitudes, interests, personality patterns, good and weak points of their children
- (ii) Improving parent-child relationships
- (iii) Improving parent, school and community relationships
- (iv) Improving study habits of children

- (v) Helping the parents in solving the problems of their children and assisting them in making adjustments.

Least Expectancy Regarding The Organisation of Guidance Programme In Schools :-

Guidance is not a celestial plant that may take root in any sole. The ground conducive to its growth has to be provided. Accepted that it is not possible to start with all the services, i.e., Data collection service, occupational information service, self-inventory service, counselling service, vocational preparatory service, placement service, Follow up service etc. in the schools, yet a beginning may be made with the humble effort to have some minimum programme of guidance. The following points may be mentioned in this connection:

1. Minimum services -The minimum services which must be started in every school are data collection, occupational information and elementary counselling.
2. Provision in time-table-There must be a provision for guidance programme in the school time-table as well as in the school budget.
3. Co-operation-There must be active co-operation among all the stakeholders, i.e., teachers, staff, counselor, parents etc. A Committee for guidance may be set up. The head of the institution should be the administrative head and the counsellor should be the advisory head of the committee.
4. Trained counselors-There must be trained counselors one for every 200 students in every school.

5. Facilities to teachers- Facilities to the teachers should be provided so that they may become increasingly efficient in guidance work. These include orientation courses and seminars in guidance for as many teachers as possible to enable them to assess and evaluate pupils' needs and the ways to meet them.
6. Guidance Bureau- In every school, there should be a Guidance Bureau in the charge of a teacher having a sound knowledge of psychology and guidance techniques. He should acquaint himself with the environment and orient the pupils accordingly in educational, vocational, psychological or personal areas.

In order to make teachers effectively sensitized, the secondary schools in west Bengal may implement the following Guidance Programme by providing :

Classroom Guidance :-

1. Academic skills support
2. Organizational, study and test-taking skills

3. Career planning
4. Education in understanding self and others
5. Coping strategies
6. Peer relationships and effective social skills
7. Communication, problem-solving, decision-making, conflict resolution and study skills.
8. Career awareness and the world of work
9. Multicultural/diversity awareness

Individual Student Planning

1. Goal setting
2. Academic Plan
3. Career Plan
4. Problem-Solving
5. Education in understanding of self, including strengths and weaknesses
6. Transition plans

Responsive Services :-

- a) Individual and small-group counselling
- b) Individual/family/School crisis intervention
- c) Peer facilitation
- d) Consultation/Collaboration
- e) Referrals

Review of Related Studies

1. Branwhite, Tony (2000) "Helping Adolescents In School", Greenwood

publishing Group. In this book, Dr. Branwhite provides a unique analysis of the view of adolescents based upon applied research. This book identifies the challenges facing adolescents and highlights their coping skills.

2. Burnard, Philip (1999) "Counselling skills training : A Source Book of activities" (First Indian Paperback edition) Viva Books private Ltd. India. This book provides all the information a trainer will need to run the counselling activities. The activities, 80 in all, cover the full breadth of counseling skills. This stimulating resource will be of great value and interest to trainers, teachers, health care workers.
3. Agrawal, R.(2006) "Educational, vocational Guidance and Counselling : Principles, Techniques and Programmes" Shipra, New Delhi. this book covers a wide spectrum of topics relating to guidance and counseling-its concepts, social and ethical issues, organization of Guidance services in schools etc. The subject is treated not purely from a theoretical perspective, but also with a practical orientation.
4. Edwards, Richard, Harrison, R.,Tait, Alan (1998) *Telling Tale : Perspectives on Guidance and counselling in Learning*", Routledge. This book looks more at the provision made for the different types of guidance and counselling in learning available. This book is dealt with a case-study based approach to guidance.
5. Palmer, Stephen U McMahan, G.(1997) *Handbook of counselling*",Routledge. This book explores the major areanas and setting in which counseling is practised. This book provides a definitive source of information in training and practice.
6. Hornby, Garry, Hall, C., Hall, E. (2003)"Counselling Pupils in Schools:Skills and Strategies for Teachers" Routledge. This book is a comprehensive introductory guide on counselling skills and strategies for teachers in order for them to take control of problems involving students and parents.
7. Gibson, R.L..Mitchell, Marianne (1999)"Introduction to counselling and Guidance" Prentice Hall International. This book provides an introduction to counselling text that includes comprehensive coverage of process, setting, and theory. This work presents practical examples and discussions of the major facets of counselling in school and non-school settings.

Purpose/Characteristics of a comprehensive Guidance Programme :

- * Careful and consistent development.
- * Developmental, Preventive, remedial, corrective
- * Addresses the needs of the students.
- * Goal-oriented and accountable
- * integral Part of the school curriculum, complementing other school activities.

* Balanced, encompassing the four fundamental fields/areas of Guidance:

- 1) Personal
- 2) Educational
- 3) Social
- 4) Vocational/Career.

* Determines the services to be offered:

- Orientation
- Information
- Behaviour modification through counselling etc.

* utilizes all staff members in their appropriate roles

* Creates an atmosphere of team-work

* Should benefit all students rather than just a few

An opinionnaire prepared for the teachers of secondary schools seeking their outlook and attitude to Guidance and Counselling :

The following statements represent opinions, and your agreement or disagreement will be determined on the basis of your particular beliefs. Kindly check your position on the scale as the statement first impresses you. Indicate what you believe, rather than what you think you should believe.

1. All the problems related to life can never be solved alone.
2. It is always necessary for getting advice/suggestion to remove the prevailing obstacles in personal and social life.

Sample Guidance and Counseling Programme :-

NEED	STRATEGY	SERVICE	RESOURCE (Human & Material)
Understanding the self	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case study - Discussion - Role - playing 	Guidance	Teacher, pupils, handouts etc.
Study Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussion - Peer coaching - Study groups 	Information Counselling	Library, Video, Pupils, teacher-counsellor
Adolescent Reproductive Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Talk - Video show - Group Debate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Counselling - Information - Consultation - Appraisal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Counsellor - Video Cassette - TV - Pupils, posters -Teacher, handouts
Interview skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video show - Role playing - Discussion - Reading 	Career Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video Cassette - Handouts - Students

School Guidance and Counselling Services

Personal development/social development

Educational development/career development

Programmatic(student contact)		Structural (non-student contact)	
1	2	3	4
Counselling	Prevention	Guidance Education	Consultation, Planning & Coordination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Individual Counselling *Small group counseling *Crisis counseling *Career counseling *Referrals *Peer helping programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Primary, secondary, tertiary plans and programmes *individual assessment co-ordinated student support team activities *Student advocacy *Transitional planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Integrated, developmental student learning out comes *Classroom-based guidance instruction and assessment *personal/social development *Educational development *Career development *Group guidance activities *Professional resources *Post secondary education and career resource materials and programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination *Professional development *Counselling and collaboration *Programme management and operations *Data-informed decision-making *Advocacy for guidance related classroom-based learning outcomes *needs assessments *Time allotments and class load management *Calendar of activities *School-based planning

3. The school-going adolescents are not at all able to cope up with the fast changing environment.
4. Teachers must not prohibit impatience, mental instability, maladjustment, violence of their students by giving punishment
5. A teacher should have a strong impact on guiding or directing his students
6. A teacher being a role-model is able to motivate his students a lot
7. Teachers face more conflicts related to students' life and education than parents
8. The knowledge of guidance and counseling is essential for teacher for guiding students
9. Most teachers are sympathetic and serious for advising students in needs
10. It is essential to start reliable vocational guidance in schools.
11. A comprehensive teachers' orientation in guidance and counseling should be mandatory.

12. It is feasible to introduce a Guidance cell in schools.
13. Arrangements of periods can be affordable in the time table for guidance in schools
14. Many problems can be controlled in time if we believe in the motto, "prevention is better than cure".
15. Teachers should discuss regularly about the students' personality development in the parent teacher meeting.

Result/Findings : Responses of Teachers Towards Positive Attitude on Guidance and Counselling

An opinionnaire or a five-point attitude scale containing 15 statements has been administered to 60 teachers who are teaching in secondary schools of six districts in West Bengal. The responses of teachers towards positive attitude on guidance and counseling has been shown by the following bar diagram (fig-1).

The spirit or essence of the responses shows a positive and inclined attitude of the teachers

TEACHERS ARE REQUESTED TO TICK(√) IN THE APPROPRIATE BOXES

	Q.1	Q.2	Q.3	Q.4	Q.5	Q.6	Q.7	Q.8	Q.9	Q.10	Q.11	Q.12	Q.13	Q.14	Q.15
Strongly Agree															
Agree															
Undecided															
Disagree															
Strongly Disagree															

SA-STRONGLY AGREE, AG-AGREE, UN-UNDECIDED, DA-DISAGREE, SD-STRONGLY DISAGREE

FIGURE-1

of secondary schools in West Bengal about Guidance and counseling sensitization programme in schools. The result shows that the number of agreement is distinctly higher than that of the disagreement. Hence, it can be clearly interpreted that teachers' positive attitudes unquestionably lead to guidance and counseling programme in schools. we can come to the conclusion that positive attitude in guidance and counselling persists in the teaching community of West Bengal.

Limitations

Though organization of Guidance services is essential to channelize the energy of modern youth in the proper direction for the welfare of the individual and the society, yet in our country guidance services are at the initial stage and have to be geared properly to meet the challenges. Some of the limitations are as follows:

1. Guidance services whether personal, educational and vocational have been still are limited due to the lack of properly trained personnel in the profession
2. It is wrong and unrealistic to assume that guidance is a panacea for all educational problems. It is simply one of the means of education for personalizing its service and goals.
3. Guidance in schools is limited in what it can do in terms of career and occupational choices but how most effectively to combine student abilities with career and occupational choices is the greatest problem which the guidance workers face in our state. The entire effort is very much sporadic. There is no central coordination agency.

4. Guidance workers use tests to evaluate the potentialities of individuals but the reliability of testing instrument as well as untrained persons who are using it is open to question.
5. The conditions of living in our society are gradually becoming too complex. It is very difficult enough for a person to decide quickly the problems of another in any simple setting.

Conclusion

There is no denying that revolutionary changes have been taken place in all domains of life in the last two decades due to the effects of liberalization, privatization and globalization. Traditional concepts and practices of guidance and counseling would not be able to cope with the growing problems emerging in human life. The printing and electronic media constantly try to sensitize people about the exorbitant needs and importance of guiding students. We are living in such a complex world where erosion of values has become a daily phenomenon. If 'learning to live together' is one of the shelters that modern education provides, we have to inculcate and develop the spirit of 'togetherness' among ourselves and that would be the only shelter for our existence. No matter whether infrastructure will be available or not, administrative inclination or opposition, environmental support or restraint: teachers should have a strong goodwill and determination in favour of guidance service in schools. Sympathy is not enough; teachers should have boundless empathy. "To assume that a worthwhile programme cannot be implemented with a staff or organizational pattern less than ideal would be administrative suicide. To maintain an ideal objective and to work towards it should result in an effective

educational programme, provided a real effort has been made". Two kinds of services can be immediately undertaken for a minimum essential guidance programme in schools (1) Developmental, and (2) Orientational. The developmental services include co-curricular activities like hobby-clubs, dramas, debates, self-government, social service programmes, games and sports, 'Know your neighbour' campaign etc. Orientational services are meant to help each student to become fully acquainted with himself and his environment so that he is enabled to take right steps without formal assistance from others; in a word, he will be capable of self-direction.

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